

THE MOST EFFECTIVE WAYS TO BOOST STUDENTS' LISTENING SKILLS AT SCHOOLS

Zebo Botirova Xakimjon's daughter

Namangan State University,

Associate professor Department of
English language and literature, PhD

E-mail: ziziko_90@mail.ru

Sayfullayeva Nigora Gofurjon's daughter,

Namangan State University,

A master's student of English literature

Abstract This article deals with the most interesting and efficient learning styles in the improvement of pupils' listening skills. During two years of teaching sphere, I have collected a lot of data regarding the problems that most pupils are encountering while learning a second language these days. Thanks to the research questionnaire which I have conducted recently, I found new ways. I will introduce the most productive approaches which help to enhance students' listening abilities. Besides, I will also provide some ubiquitous difficulties in listening comprehension and in what ways they can be avoided. The tips in my article can be employed in the primary and secondary schools or in any language educational auditories.

Key words: Listening, receptive skills, communication, recognition, affectivity, listening competence, familiar words, role-plays, topic vocabulary.

Аннотация В этой статье обсуждаются наиболее интересные и эффективные средства стилей обучения для улучшения навыков слушания учащихся. За два года преподавания я собрала много данных о проблемах, с которыми в наши дни сталкивается большинство учеников при изучении второго языка. Благодаря опроснику, который я провела недавно, я нашла новые пути. Я представлю наиболее продуктивные подходы, которые помогают улучшить навыки слушания учащихся. Кроме того, я также расскажу о некоторых типичных трудностях с пониманием речи на слух и о том, как их можно избежать. Советы из моей статьи можно использовать в начальных и средних школах или в любых языковых учебных аудиториях.

Ключевые слова: аудирование, рецептивные навыки, общение, узнавание, эффективность, умение слушать, знакомые слова, ролевые игры, тематический словарь

Annotatsiya Ushbu maqolada o'quvchilarning tinglash ko'nikmalarini oshirishdagi uslublarni o'rganishning eng qiziqarli va samarali usullari haqida so'z boradi. Ikki yillik o'qitish sohasida men hozirgi kunda ko'pchilik o'quvchilar ikkinchi tilni o'rganishda duch keladigan muammolar haqida ko'plab ma'lumotlarni to'pladim. Yaqinda o'tkazgan tadqiqot so'rovnomasi tufayli men yangi usullarni topdim. Men o'quvchilarning tinglash qobiliyatini oshirishga yordam beradigan eng samarali usullar bilan tanishtiraman. Bundan tashqari, men tinglab tushunishda ba'zi ko'p uchraydigan qiyinchiliklari va ularni qanday yo'l bilan oldini olish mumkinligini aytib beraman. Mening maqolamdagi maslahatlar boshlang'ich va o'rta maktablarda yoki istalgan til o'quv auditoriyalarida qo'llanilishi mumkin.

Tayanch tushunchalar: Tinglash, qabul qilish qobiliyati, muloqot, tanib olish, ta'sirchanlik, tinglash qobiliyati, tanish so'zlar, rolli o'yinlar, mavzu lug'ati

INTRODUCTION

As you probably know, listening is the key to all other three skills acquisition. For example, without knowing the pronunciation of any words in a language it is impossible to read and comprehend it and certainly, writing skills come the same way. Before speaking, language learners listen and then they will interpret what they comprehend through listening. There is no interaction without listening. The listening skill develops much faster than other three language skills, which in turn suggests that it can facilitate the emergence of the other language skills (Oxford, 1990). People started to consider listening comprehension significant importance in the 1970s when Gary (1975) claimed concentration on listening in the first stage of learning a second language creates four different types of benefits: cognitive, efficiency, utility and affective. The cognitive advantage is that while learners listen some sort of information after that they acquire it in a

natural way. Listening should be stressed before speaking since the recognition of knowledge is required process. Many researchers supported the idea that listening is first and foremost skill that must be acquired when language learners start learning a second language. Listening also efficient way not to start speaking immediately but first listening a language. This allows any kind of language learners to have some time to comprehend and decide about what to start communication. Third benefit is utility or the usefulness of listening comprehension. According to research conducted in the spheres of interaction adults spend 40-50% communication time listening 25-30% speaking, 9% writing and nearly 11-16% reading (Rivers in Gilman and Moody, 1984). The last advantage is known as the affectivity of the listening skill. Learners often suffer from embarrassment and sometimes disappointment and lack of self-confidence when they are forced to talk in front of many people. If there was no pressure they can relax and focus on improvement of the listening abilities. Because listening helps to achieve students successes they feel much more motivated and keep learning. A qualitative analyses show that a better listener focused on key information. The general approach was much more of a top-down one, while less effective listeners were more reliant on strategies for word by word decoding (bottom-up strategies) (O. Malley and Chamot, 1990). The listeners store of background information can relate to the context, the topic, the type of text, conventions of rhetoric and discourse organisation. This prior knowledge becomes helpful in decoding a message even when the message has not been heard in its entirety (Peterson, 2001). As the same time of popularity of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) methodology, listening started to get importance as the CLT method caused the need to learn listening for the preparation of fruitful oral communication. Besides, now that technologies are improving and this results in emphasis on teaching listening as an crucial language skill. Researches by Rubin (1994), Lynch (1998), Flowerdew and Miller (2005) and other many noticeable studies have contributed to teach listening with new approaches.

Literature and methods

There are a plenty of exams that help to identify pupils listening competences, as you probably know. For instance, in International exams students hear a different types of accents of a second language. There can be following tasks including multiple choices, matching, classifications, short-answer questions, table/flow charts completions, sentence or summary completions, labeling a diagram, a map or a plan and others. There were many researches conducted to identify exact causes for the problems of language learner's in listening skills. For instance, the research conducted in State Islamic University of Alauddin Makassar. Thirty seven senior students of English Education Department were taken as subjects for this research. They were given questionnaires and interviews relating to the listening comprehension. The results showed that Listening was the most difficult skill to acquire for students who learn a foreign language. The most noticeable reasons included pronunciation, dialects, and low quality of listening materials. To help solve these problems Lecturers and teachers should provide their students as many native speakers dialogues as possible and improve their different topics' vocabulary to familiarize them. These all were given the teacher as suggestions. I and my two colleagues analyzed the books that school pupils read in 4 countries such as Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Tadjikistan. Many textbooks and other books like Raymond Murphy were always taught in many countries to obtain English language. Many people think before making sentences pupils should learn grammar rules. I, personally, have been encountered many advanced English non-native speakers who can easily understand and speak English very well. Most of them claim that they were not obsessed with grammar rules at school but acquire the language naturally by creating an atmosphere for speaking and utilizing the real speakers role-plays. Books which I noted above do not compose of any listening activities. Even though grammar is important it does not mean that beginners do not have to learn listening first. I think listening is a crucial competence that help learn other language skills. On the 15 of January 2023 I interviewed over five nine listening holders from IELTS exam in recent years. I had prepared 6 questions beforehand and

called them to come the interview. And when they came I gave my prepared questions. Even the questions were unfamiliar for them 3 out of 5 holders replied the same for the questions like "what is the most difficult part of listening?", "What do you think why you have taken the highest scores from listening?" They said the hardest was multiple choice questions since all the tasks look tricky and take time to understand as they are longer compared to other listening activities such as sentence completions. Additionally, they said to solve such kind of tasks pupils need to know topic vocabulary as much as possible. This helps them to find out the key words and the correct order of information given in listening answers. For question about their great success in the exam they declared it was because of the motivational videos and the hobbies they do during their free time. If you like what you are doing and listen only the ones you are interested in, you will learn a language unconsciously. Listening experts also added the proverb "Rome was not built in a day" -by motivating themselves not to stop on the half way pupils should do listening regularly. Their hard work will definitely will be paid off after sometime. The interview proved that the most effective way to improve listening is to listen for fun on a daily basis. Students should choose topics that are interesting for them. For instance, if they like professional tennis they should listen to podcasts about professional tennis. If they love Roman history, listening to stories about Roman history can be fun. Listening is considered to be as a receptive skill. As well as, it is absorbed passively- meaning pupils obtain this competence only after long-term studies and by familiarizing their ears to the language they are learning. In order not to get bored by forcing themselves to practice a thousand of listening exercises, pupils need to listen only the topics which are really interested them.

Results

As subjects for my research, I chose 2 group pupils at specialized school whose levels were completely different from each other. There were overall 50 pupils were taken as the subjects of my research. Some students were in intermediate, some in an upper-intermediate level students. At first, I decided to

hand in the same listening audio with the same activities for all level students The listening was about School life and the vocabulary of the conversation were for upper-intermediate students. Results were not considerably different. Nearly 90 % of the students found it easy to understand and find solutions to the answers. Only 10 % of the students were somehow confused some task relating to completing sentences with the words given in a conversation. Surprisingly, the intermediate students were good at listening tasks even though it was thought to be a hard for them to solve since their levels were lower than others'. In order to know the reason I asked why whether they were lucky to guess the words or they understood the listening conversation good enough. 22 students out of 24 replied that they could absorb the listening because of the fact that they know the topic well and were quite interested in it. Only 2 of them considered themselves lucky to guess most answers correctly. As coming for upper level students those who made mistakes said because they were somehow careless about the answers. They thought they could find them with no effort this caused them to be confused in the end. After that I gave another listening task but with different and a completely unfamiliar topic for all level pupils. This time the results were very different from the first time. It is proved that the pupils who like the topic can catch the context of listening dialogues and podcasts straightforward, on the other hand, it is difficult to understand if the students do not like the given topic.

Discussion

Regardless of the level for any students it seems quite hard to solve the listening tasks relating to unknown theme. The outcomes of the experiment also showed that since most students interests differ from one another, they can not be forced to learn only one topic for all. As the researches showed that there are some effective ways to boost listening comprehension of students at schools:

1. Listening for fun

Pupils will do listening for fun. They listen to topics which are interesting for them. To improve listening skills, doing exercise regularly is the key. Pupils cannot be forced to learn something they do not want to learn. Therefore, the only way to attract their attention, they should be allowed to listen as they wish. If the student's major is like in the spheres of math, one should try to teach them math phrases and the lessons relating to math. This helps teachers keep their students interested in listening tasks since they wonder to know more about things they do not know about their favourite topics.

2. Familiarizing the topics

Before giving any topics, students should know some vocabulary and detailed information about the topic. For instance, if the listening is about animals, pupils should have a wide range of vocabulary to solve tasks. If you give them unfamiliar topics like organising a camp at university without explaining what it is about, pupils will be confused and write incorrect answers.

3. Listening at different speeds

When pupils do listening, they should listen at various speeds. This aids them to guess the missed parts and catch up with the speaker's speech easily while during important listening exams. For instance, people who listen to one podcast over and over but at a different speed have found it straightforward to understand even the confusing parts of any topic without seeing the subtitles.

3. Doing an active listening

4. Listening can be understood easily when pupils take notes. During this, pupils will learn to concentrate on the sentences for a long time without any interruptions. Active listening helps not only for listening but it is also a great way to develop speaking and writing as well.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in the process of learning any kind of a language, listening is the most important key to master other competences. Therefore, since the 1970s, researchers and language scientists are looking for the best ways to learn and

improve this skill. I also made a little experiment on my students at school as I mentioned above. In order that student's improve their listening competence, they should be ready to use to any effective strategies. Searching for the answers and being aware of many experiments done by renowned researchers before, I concluded four different and fascinating approaches that students can apply to improve the pupils' listening competence. There is no need to hire any instructor if the students are in pre- intermediate or higher level, all they need to do is remind themselves to do listening regularly. However, learners should not focus on improving this skills only, they are also supposed to try other skills as well. Students should bear in mind that listening is not something that be absorbed in a day or a week. It is time-consuming process. I can suggest using most effective approaches which help them with this. Until now I have many students who took international language exams, the tips I mentioned could help them to get their listening results much better.

References

1. Oxford, R. 1990. Language learning strategies: What every teacher should know.
2. O Malley, J.M. and A. Chamot. (1990). Strategies used by Second L Learners Cambridge: CUP.
3. Gilman, R. A. & Moody, L. M. (1984). Language learning background factors and ESL proficiency. Foreign Language Annals
4. Gary, J.O. (1975) Delayed oral practice in initial stages of second language learning' in W.C. Ritchie (ed) Second Language Acquisition Research: Issues and Implications. New York: Academic Press.
5. English for Exams listening for IELTS. Fiona Aish, Jom Tomlinson (2011) [Collins]
6. Botirova, Z. X. K., & Asadova, R. I. Q. (2023). A CLOSER VIEW ON ANCIENT MEMORIAL OF YUSUF KHOS HAJIB "KUTADGU BILIG". *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(15), 125-132.

7. Botirova, Z. X. K., & qizi Jurabayeva, G. U. (2023). TEACHING APPROACHES OF SPEAKING IN ESL CLASSES. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(11), 4-9.

8. Botirova, Z. X. K., & Asadova, R. I. Q. (2023). A CLOSER VIEW ON ANCIENT MEMORIAL OF YUSUF KHOS HAJIB “KUTADGU BILIG”. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(15), 125-132.

9. қизи Ботирова, З. Х. (2020). Principles of taking into consideration language skill of students in teaching vocabulary of English. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 2(3), 351-355.

10. qizi Botirova, Z. X. (2023). A VIEW ON AMERICAN ROMANTICISM THROUGH EDGAR ALLAN POE’S POETRY. *SCHOLAR*, 1(34), 30-36.

11. qizi Botirova, Z. X., & qizi Nabiyeva, Z. O. (2023). LAKUNA ATAMASINING LINGVOMADANIY AHAMIYATI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(16), 293-299.

12. qizi Abdullayeva, N. K., qizi Ahunjanova, M. S., & Botirova, Z. (2023). BRIDGING THE LACUNA: ADDRESSING LINGUISTIC GAPS AND EXPLORING SOLUTIONS. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(11), 239-242.

13. Botirova, Z. X., & qizi Ahmedova, M. B. (2023). THE MODERN TECHNIQUES OF TEACHING VOCABULARY IN EFL CLASSES. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(15), 242-246.

14. qizi Ahunjanova, M. S., & Botirova, Z. (2023). EXPLORING THE THEORY OF ARCHETYPES. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(15), 251-254.

15. Botirova, Z. X., & Bekmatova, N. I. (2023). “UR, TO ‘QMOQ” O ‘ZBEK XALQ ERTAGINING INGLIZ TILIDAGI PROTOTIPI, O ‘XSHASHLIKLAR VA FARQLAR.:“UR, TO ‘QMOQ” O ‘ZBEK XALQ ERTAGINING INGLIZ TILIDAGI PROTOTIPI, O ‘XSHASHLIKLAR VA FARQLAR.

16. Botirova, Z., Rasulova, G., & Sevara, N. (2023). ACTIVATION OF EDUCATIONAL AND COGNITIVE ACTIVITY OF YOUNGER

SCHOOLCHILDREN BY MEANS OF DIDACTIC GAMES ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE SUBJECT "ENGLISH LANGUAGE". *Research Focus*, 2(11), 76-79.

17. Kizi, B. Z. X. (2023). Role of digital technologies in education. *Строительство и образование*, 3(5), 28-34.

18. Жалолов, Ш., & Ботирова, З. (2016). К ВОПРОСУ УПОТРЕБЛЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОЙ ФРАЗЕОЛОГИИ В ЮРИДИЧЕСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ. In *Современные тенденции развития аграрного комплекса* (pp. 1716-1718).

19. Umrzoqov, I. I., Botirova, Z. H., & Valiyev, Q. O. (2019). ENGLISH LANGUAGE AND ITS VARIETIES. *Экономика и социум*, (5 (60)), 214-216.

20. Umrzoqov, I. I., Kizi, B. Z., & Sharipova, A. S. (2019). DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE. *Экономика и социум*, (3 (58)), 66-67.

21. Kizi, B. Z. X., & Kizi, A. G. A. (2023). ON TRAINING OF PEDAGOGICAL STAFF IN CONDITIONS OF DIGITALIZATION OF EDUCATION.

22. Jalolov, S. (2019). Role of peer observation in foreign language teaching. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 1(12), 274-277.

23. Israilovich, I. U. (2019). Practical Strategies to Teach Vocabulary Through Games in EFL Beginner Classes: the Case Study of Some Secondary Schools in Namangan Region. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 2(6), 94-96.

24. Botirova, Z. H. K. (2020). Developing of lexical skills in English in secondary schools. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 2(1), 199-203.

25. Kizi, B. Z. X. (2022). EXERCISE ANALYSIS DESIGNED TO DEVELOP LEXICAL COMPETENCE IN 6TH GRADE ENGLISH TEXTBOOKS. *Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities*, 2(1.5 Pedagogical sciences).

26. Botirova, Z. X. Q. (2020). The importance of age factors on teaching English in grades 5-6. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 2(11), 381-384.

27. Botirova, Z. X. (2021). Personality-orientated approach to teaching english vocabulary. In *МИРОВАЯ НАУКА 2021. ПРОБЛЕМЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ* (pp. 6-8).